

Improving the competitiveness of forage and fruit production in agroforestry systems

www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet/

Over the last decade, farmers are facing increasing sensitivity to weather conditions of berries and vegetables. According to researchers, this is due to the more frequent extremes caused by climate change and the change in radiation conditions.

This affects to the growth of plants and them more difficult to absorb nutrients, while impairing the quality and quantity of the crop (yield loss, sunburn patches on the fruit and leaf, reduced resistance to pathogens and harmful organisms).

Early experience of Hungarian farmers working in cooperation with the University of Sopron and the results of the experiments carried out at the National Agricultural Research and Innovation Centre so far show that this problem can be eliminated or at least significantly mitigated by partial shading of certain forage species (eg. alfalfa), as well as understory berry species / varieties such as raspberries, currants and strawberries. However, for berries, the extent and sign of the effect may depend largely on the varieties.

As regards forage production, [results from an experiment](#) carried out in AGFORWARD project show that in alley cropping with a combination of

alfalfa and fast growing tree species (Paulownia sp.) can increase of the quantity and quality of yield.

Further information:

<https://www.agforward.eu/index.php/hu/szantofoe/ldi-agroerdeszeti-rendszerek-magyarorszagon.html>

Figure 1. Partial shading of alfalfa by trees in a Hungarian AF system (above). Photo: Vityi A. Visitors in the AF experimental site with berries of the National Agricultural Research and Innovation Centre, Hungary (below). Ref: NAIK (<https://www.naik.hu>)

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